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E-mail: nazirovm@gmail.com**BASKETBOL SHITI ORQALI AMALGA OSHIRILGAN TO'P TASHLASHLAR (BANK-SHOT)
SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILLARI**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17994758>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada 14–16 yoshli qiz basketbolchilarda basketbol shitidan foydalanish (bank-shot) texnikasining samaradorligi dastlabki natijalar asosida tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqotda nazorat va tajriba guruhleri o'rtasida turli pozitsiyalardan (F1–F10) tashlangan zarbalar aniqligi solishtirilib, statik va o'yin sharoitidagi natijalar baholandi. Dastlabki testlar ko'rsatdiki, markaziy pozitsiyalardan Shit orqali top otishaniqligi 60–70 % atrofida bo'lsa, himoyachi qarshiligida bu ko'rsatkich 25 % gacha kamaydi. Nazorat va tajriba guruhleri boshlang'ich ko'rsatkichlari statistik jihatdan teng bo'lib, keyingi bosqichlarda maxsus mashg'ulotlar samaradorligini aniqlash uchun sharoit yaratdi. Tadqiqot natijalari Shit orqali top otishtexnikasining o'quv-mashg'ulot jarayonida yetarlicha qo'lla-nilmagani, ammo uni tizimli o'rgatish yosh sportchilar samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qilishini ko'rsatdi.

Kalif so'zlar: basketbol shiti, to'p tashlash aniqligi, shit orqali top otishsamaradorligi, biomexanik model, 14–16 yoshli qizlar, pedagogik tajriba

Kirish

Basketbol sportida to'pni savatga tashlash texnikasi o'yinning eng hal qiluvchi elementlaridan biridir. Shu jarayonda basketbol shiti (backboard)dan foydalanish orqali amalga oshiriladigan zarbalar — bank-shotlar — yuqori aniqlik va ishonchlilikni ta'minlovchi usullardan hisoblanadi. Xalqaro ilmiy tadqiqotlar, xususan Shimoliy Karolina shtati universiteti muhandislarining kompyuter simulyatsiyalari, 3–3,5 metr masofada bank-shotning to'g'ridan-to'g'ri zarbaga nisbatan 20 % samaraliroq ekanini ko'rsatgan. Biroq zamonaviy o'quv-mashg'ulotlarda shit orqali top otishtexnikasiga yetarlicha e'tibor berilmayapti. Aksariyat yosh basketbolchilar uch ochkolik yoki kuchli dunk zarbalarga intilib, oddiyroq va ishonchli shit orqali top otishuslubidan kam foydalanadilar. Shu sababli, 14–16 yoshli qizlarda shit orqali top otishtexnikasining dastlabki ko'rsatkichlarini aniqlash, ularning kuchli va zaif tomonlarini tahlil qilish, keyingi mashg'ulotlarda metodik yondashuv ishlab chiqish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

1. Basketbol shitidan foydalanishning nazariy asoslari

Basketbol shitidan foydalanish texnikasi

zarbaning biomexanik modeli bilan izohlanadi: to'p orqa spin bilan shitga urilib, kuchning bir qismini yo'qotadi va yumshoq trayektoriya bilan savatga tushadi. Tadqiqotlar ko'rsatadiki, ~45–55° chiqish burchagi, 3 Hz atrofidagi orqa aylanish (backspin) va shit ustidagi optimal "ko'z oynak" nuqtasiga yo'naltirilgan zarba eng yuqori samaradorlikni beradi. Jon Vuden singari afsonaviy trenerlar ham yaqin va o'rta masofadagi barcha zarbalarni imkon qadar shitdan foydalanib amalga oshirishni tavsiya qilgan. Shunga qaramay, estetik stereotiplar ("toza swish"ning chiroyliligi) va uch ochkolik zarbalarning ustunligi tufayli shit orqali top otishbugungi basketbolda kamroq qo'llanilmoqda.

Tadqiqot metodlari

Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida Farg'ona, Andijon va Namangan viloyatlaridagi sport maktablarida shug'ullanayotgan 14–16 yoshli qiz basketbolchilar tanlandi. Ishtirokchilar nazorat va tajriba guruhlariga ajratildi. Testlar basketbol maydonidagi 10 ta belgilangan nuqtadan (F1–F10) turib shitdan foydalanilgan zarbalar asosida o'tkazildi.

Oddiy statik otish (raqibsiz)

2×2 va 3×3 kichik o'yin sharoiti

1-jadval
Basketbol shitidan foydalanish (bank-shot) texnikasining nazariy asoslari

Ko'rsatkich	Ilmiy tavsif	Samaradorlikka ta'siri
Zarba chiqish burchagi	45–55° oralig'i optimal hisoblanadi	To'p trayektoriyasini savatga moslashtiradi
To'p aylanishi (backspin)	O'rtacha 3 Hz orqa aylanish	Shit bilan to'qnashuvda energiya yo'qotilishini kamaytiradi
Nishon nuqtasi	Shit ustidagi "ko'z oynak" (Shit orqali top otishpoint)	To'pning yumshoq qaytishini ta'minlaydi
Biomekanik model	Shitga urilgan to'pning kinetik energiyasi qisman so'nadi	Aniqlik oshadi
Trenerlik yondashuvi	J. Vuden tomonidan yaqin va o'rta masofalarda tavsiya etilgan	O'yin samaradorligini oshiradi
Zamonaviy tendensiya	"Swish" zarbalarga estetik ustunlik berilishi	Shit orqali top otishkamroq qo'llaniladi

Himoyachi qarshiligida (bloklashga urinuvchi raqib)

Sakrab otish

Ko'rsatkichlar urilgan/urinishlar nisbatida hisoblab chiqildi.

3. Dastlabki ko'rsatkichlar tahlili

Natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki:

Statik sharoitda o'yinchilar markaziy nuqtalardan (F5–F6) o'rtacha 65–70 % aniqlikka erishdi, qisqa burchaklarda esa bu ko'rsatkich ~50 % bo'ldi.

2x2 va 3x3 o'yin sharoitida shit orqali top otishsamaradorligi pasaydi va ~40–50 % oralig'ida bo'ldi.

Himoyachi qarshiligida aniqlik eng past darajaga tushib, o'rtacha 25 % ni tashkil etdi.

Sakrash bilan otish statik natijalarga yaqin bo'lib, ~55–60 % ko'rsatkich qayd etildi.

Muhim jihati shundaki, nazorat va tajriba guruhlar orasida boshlang'ich test natijalari o'rtasida ishonchli statistik farq kuzatilmadi ($p > 0,05$). Bu esa keyingi bosqichda tajriba guruhiga maxsus mashg'ulot dasturi qo'llanilganda farqlarni aniqlash uchun

qulay sharoit yaratadi.

Muhokama

Dastlabki natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yosh basketbolchilar shit orqali top otishtexnikasida nazariy bilimlarga ega bo'lsalar-da, real o'yin sharoitida bu ko'nikmalar barqaror emas. Ayniqsa, himoyachi qarshiligida va bosim ostida shit orqali top otishsamaradorligi keskin pasayadi.

Bu natijalar xorijiy tadqiqotlar bilan uyg'un: N.S. Morozova (2009) o'z ishida maxsus metodika asosida shit orqali top otishaniqligini 5–10 % ga oshirish mumkinligini isbotlagan. Silverberg va hamkorlari (2011) esa optimal "V-shaklli nishon nuqtalari" dan tashlangan zarbalar 20 % gacha yuqori natija berishini ko'rsatgan.

Shunday ekan, 14–16 yoshli qiz basketbolchilarda shit orqali top otishko'nikmalarini mustahkamlash uchun maxsus mashg'ulot tizimlarini joriy etish, vizual ko'makchi belgilar ("ko'z oynak" metodikasi) va bosim ostidagi mashqlarni ko'paytirish zarur.

Xulosa

Basketbol shitidan foydalanish (bank-

2-jadval
Shit orqali top otish zarbalarini bajarish sharoitlari

Mashq sharoiti	Tavsif
Statik otish	Raqibsiz, joydan turib
Kichik o'yinlar	2x2 va 3x3 format
Himoyachi qarshiligida	Bloklashga urinuvchi raqib mavjud
Sakrab otish	Harakatda va sakrash bilan bajariladigan zarba

shot) texnikasi nazariy jihatdan yuqori samaradorlikka ega bo'lsa-da, amaliy mashg'ulotlarda yetarlicha o'rgatilmayapti. Dastlabki testlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, markaziy nuqtalarda Shit orqali top otishaniqligi 65–70 % bo'lsa, himoyachi qarshiligida bu ko'rsatkich atigi 25 % ga tushadi. Nazorat va tajriba guruhlarini boshlang'ich natijalari teng bo'lib, keyingi maxsus mashg'ulotlar samaradorligini baholash uchun to'g'ri sharoit yaratildi. Basketbol shitidan foydalanish texnikasini tizimli o'rgatish, vizual ko'makchi vositalardan foydalanish va real o'yin sharoitlariga mos mashqlar joriy etish yosh sportchilar samaradorligini oshirishning asosiy omilidir.

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